

A Novel Automated Water Pretreatment System for Microbial Preconcentration and DNA Extraction Using Monolithic Adsorption Filtration (MAF)

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INTRODUCTION

Rapid microbial monitoring is essential under EU Directives 2020/2184 and 2020/741, which require zero *E. coli* and a 6-log coliphage reduction in water. This work introduces an automated pretreatment system using Monolithic Adsorption Filtration (MAF) for efficient preconcentration and direct DNA extraction. Designed for in-line or field use, it detects *E. coli*, coliphages, and emerging pathogens like *Helicobacter pylori*, offering a fast, alternative to lab-based methods for water monitoring.

SYSTEM OVERVIEW

The system combines two processes: 1) two-step pathogen preconcentration via cross-flow ultrafiltration (CUF), and monolithic adsorption filtration (MAF) using DEAE-functionalized MAFs, 2) MAF-OH-based DNA extraction. This enables rapid sample-to-analyte transition for downstream qPCR detection. The in-development system supports single-use MAF disc exchange to avoid cross-contamination and maintain sample integrity. It processes up to 100 L in around 30 minutes, allowing real-time, in-line monitoring.

Figure 1: System Workflow

Figure 2: Prototype System

Figure 3: CUF & MAF procedures

RESULTS

MAF - Based Preconcentration

E. coli spiked 10⁵, 10⁶, 10⁷ cells into 10 L water showed 62.1%, 63.2%, and 35.7% recovery, respectively. Tangential flow minimized clogging and enabled efficient capture. Cleaning protocols using chlorine and distilled water, removed microbes, allowing system reusability.

MAF - Based DNA Extraction

Direct lysis on MAF columns achieved 100x DNA concentration with kit-level reproducibility. Wastewater matrix inhibition remains a challenge.

Table 1. Summary of the system's performance

Metric	Target Value	Achieved Value (preliminary)
Volume Processed	10 – 100 L	Up to 10 L
Preconcentration Efficiency	80 – 90 %	~63% for <i>E. coli</i>
DNA Extraction Efficiency	75 – 85 %	~80%
Concentration Factor	≥ 100x	100x
DNA Extraction Time	≤ 15 min	10min
Total Operation Time	≤ 30 min	~30min
Automation Level	Fully Automatic	Semi – automatic

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